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DELIVERABLE REPORT

Specialized School on Novel Accelerators for Young Scientists

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ABSTRACT

In view of the rapidly developing field of new wake field based acceleration techniques, special emphasis is needed on the issue of communication, networking and training of younger colleagues.

Unlike to the situation in the community of traditional accelerator physics and projects, the research in high gradient plasma and dielectric acceleration structures is still a new and fast evolving topic. As a natural consequence, a well-established community exists in the classical accelerator domain and a large variety of text books are available as well as lectures in a manifold of universities and institutes. In the wake acceleration domain however, we still have to fulfil the need of training and in order to improve the communication between young colleagues as well as colleagues that are entering the field, it has been decided to establish a series of lectures that will summarise the knowledge and state of the art in high gradient acceleration.

SPECIALIZED SCHOOL ON NOVEL ACCELERATORS FOR YOUNG SCIENTISTS

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Together with international experts, the plan for a dedicated accelerator school on wake acceleration has been put into practise and in a special program committee meeting the topics have been defined as well as speakers that are experts in the field and highly skilled lecturers.

The school took place in Portugal and was organised, in collaboration with the IST, Lisbon, as a full two weeks series of lectures covering a broad spectrum of relevant topics in high gradient acceleration techniques.

ARIES Consortium,2019

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Delivery Slip

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Executive summary

1.) *The field of wake acceleration is rapidly growing and new projects with a large spectrum of applications are proposed or already realised. In order to follow the request of distributing the know-how and provide a platform to train new students, a lecture series on “High Gradient Wakefield Acceleration” was organised in spring 2019.*

2.) *The agenda of the courses was set up as a full time 2 weeks course, covering a large part of the relevant topics: the basics of plasma and laser physics, the different components of a plasma wake accelerator and plasma as well as dielectric beam systems. Theoretical topics and recent experimental results obtained in different experiments were presented. An overview of the diagnostic tools and state of the art wake acceleration facilities, both present and planned completed the program. As a special item, so-called "case studies" were organised in the afternoon sessions, where the students could apply the knowledge gained in the theoretical lectures and do actual design work for a pre-defined number of tasks.*

3.) *Audience and Lecturers: The school welcomed 70 students from 25 different nationalities, 26 lecturers from 11 countries were giving courses, seminar talks or acting as tutors for the practical work of the students in the context of guided studies.*

4.) *Outreach and dissemination: In order to preserve the lectures that were presented at the school and to make them available for the whole community, it is foreseen to write proceedings that will be available in electronic as well as in printed form. They will be published as CERN yellow report towards spring of the year 2020. Access to the slides of the lectures is already available via the web page of the school.*

1. Introduction

A pre-requisite and condition "sine-qua-non" for the next step in high-energy particle acceleration is the development of new and more efficient acceleration techniques. Plasma wake fields, as well as dielectric structures have shown in the recent past very promising results and provide acceleration gradients several orders of magnitude higher than any conventional accelerating structure.

Accordingly, the study of these new acceleration techniques, finds large interest in the community of theoretical and applied accelerator physics. The field is very rapidly evolving and new projects with a large spectrum of applications are proposed that are based on high gradient wake acceleration techniques.

In accordance with the ARIES Work Program, an international school on "High Gradient Wakefield Acceleration" has been organised in spring 2019, in order to disseminate the impressive know-how accumulated in the field over the past few years, summarise the state of the art, and provide a platform to train new students joining this field. Following suggestions of the EuroNnac3 Network of ARIES (WP 5) and of an international program committee to oversee the preparation, the school was organised under the umbrella of the CERN Accelerator School, CAS. In this way, the school was not only profiting from the CAS and CERN's administrative experience, but could become a way to strengthen the collaboration between traditional accelerator physics and the new wake based systems in an attempt to close the gap between the classical and the novel acceleration techniques.

The members of the program committee have been selected from key-playing institutes in the field of plasma acceleration. After several preparatory discussions via e-mail, the decision-making meeting took place at CERN, Geneva, on 26 April 2018. The members were:

Bernhard Holzer, organiser of the school and chair of the meeting, CERN

Roger Bailey, CAS, CERN

Brigitte Cros, University Paris Sud, France

Edda Gschwendtner, Project head of the AWAKE experiment, CERN

Patric Muggli, Max-Planck-Institute Munich, Germany

Zulfikar Najmudin, Imperial College, London, UK

Luis Silva, IST, Lisbon, Portugal

Paul Andreas Walker, DESY Germany

Delphine Rivoiron, CAS secretariat

2. Structure and Organisation of the School

The school was organised by the CAS administration in collaboration with the local host selected by the Committee, Instituto Technico Superior, IST in Lisbon - as a two week, full-time lecture series.

Following introductory lectures on plasma and laser physics, the courses covered the different components of a plasma wake accelerator and plasma based as well as dielectric beam systems.

In addition, theoretical topics were covered, like the linear, non-linear and blow out regime in plasma wake physics and they were interchanged with the experimental physics program studied in different labs and recent results obtained in different experiments. An overview of the diagnostic tools and state of the art wake acceleration facilities, both present and planned, complemented the agenda of school.

Two discussion sessions gave the opportunity to ask questions, deepen the understanding and comment and complete the topics presented in the different courses.

Additional information about the school, including the access to the lecture slides is available on the Indico page of the school, <https://indico.cern.ch/event/759579/>.

As a special feature and characteristics of the CAS style for teaching, several time slots were reserved for so-called case studies. Under the guidance of the lecturers and experts in the field, the students were asked to group into several teams and do actual design studies on a pre-defined task. The results of their calculations were presented at the last afternoon of the school in the main lecture hall and the best proposals were rewarded with a little prize.

The full program of the school is shown in Fig. 1 and is available under following link:

<http://cas.web.cern.ch/sites/cas.web.cern.ch/files/programmes/sesimbra-2019-programme.pdf>

Time	Mo, 11.03.2019	Tu, 12.03.2019	Wed, 13.03.2019	Thu, 14.03.2019	Fri, 15.03.2019	Sat, 16.03.2019	Sun, 17.03.2019	Mo, 18.03.2019	Tu, 19.03.2019	Wed, 20.03.2019	Thu, 21.03.2019	Fri, 22.03.2019
09:00h		Welcome & Opening <i>B. Holzer</i>	Introduction to plasma physics II <i>P. Gibbon</i>	Plasma sources I <i>J. Osterhoff</i>	Plasma sources II <i>J. Osterhoff</i>	Plasma wake generation (non-linear) <i>L. Silva</i>		Blow out regime <i>L. Silva</i>	Particle beam diagnostics <i>B. Marchetti</i>	electron sources from plasma I <i>B. Cros</i>	staging (incl. Synchr. & tolerances) <i>C. Lindstrom</i>	
10:00h	A	Conventional Acc. & their limits I <i>M. Ferrario</i>	Laser beam physics <i>L. Corner</i>	Plasma wake generation (linear) <i>Z. Najmudin</i>	Modelling and simulation I <i>J.L. Vay</i>	Modelling and simulation II <i>J.L. Vay</i>	E	laser driver propog. in plasmas <i>S. Mangles</i>	Plasma diagnostics <i>J. Osterhoff</i>	Dielectrical Acc Structures (Theory) <i>N. Schoenenberger</i>	positron acc. in plasmas <i>S. Corde</i>	D
11:00h	R	Coffee	Coffee	Coffee	Coffee	Coffee	c	Coffee	Coffee	Coffee	Coffee	A
11:30h	I	Conventional Acc. & their limits II <i>M. Ferrario</i>	laser diagnostics <i>L. Corner</i>	Acceleration of e- in a plasma II <i>A. Thomas</i>	Injection extraction and matching I <i>M. Ferrario</i>	Modelling and simulation III <i>J.L. Vay</i>	u	Beam driven (experiment) <i>E. Gschwendtner</i>	Beam driver propogation (beams) <i>R. Assmann</i>	electron sources from plasma II <i>B. Cros</i>	case study <i>A. Walker</i>	R
12:30h	V	Lunch	Lunch	Lunch	Lunch	Lunch	r	Lunch	Lunch	Lunch	Lunch	T
14:30h	A	Introduction & hist. overview <i>V. Malka</i>	Laser driven wakefields I <i>S. Karsch</i>	Free Afternoon	Injection extraction and matching II <i>M. Ferrario</i>	Mod & simul hands on II <i>J. Vieira, R. Fonseca</i>	s	Laser driven (experiment) <i>S. Mangles</i>	Beam driven systems (PWFA) I <i>P. Muggi</i>	Dielectrical Acc Structures (Exp) <i>N. Schoenenberger</i>	Radiation generation <i>F. Albert</i>	E
15:30h	D	Introduction to plasma physics I <i>P. Gibbon</i>	Acceleration of e- in a plasma I <i>A. Thomas</i>		Applications <i>Z. Najmudin</i>	Mod & simul hands on III <i>J. Vieira, R. Fonseca</i>	n	case study <i>A. Walker</i>	Beam driven systems (PWFA) II <i>P. Muggi</i>	Seminar 2 <i>IST</i>	case study presentations <i>A. Walker</i>	D
16:30h	A	Tea	Tea		Tea	Tea		Tea	Tea	Tea	Tea	A
17:00h	Y	Introduction to laser physics I <i>L. Corner</i>	Laser driven wakefields II <i>S. Karsch</i>		Discussion 1 <i>B. Holzer</i>	Seminar I <i>IST</i>		Seminar. Acceleration of protons & ions <i>L. Willingale</i>	case study <i>A. Walker</i>	case study <i>A. Walker</i>	case study presentations <i>A. Walker</i>	Y
18:00h		1 slide / 1 minute <i>B. Holzer</i>	case study Introduction <i>A. Walker</i>		Mod & simul hands on I <i>J. Vieira, R. Fonseca</i>	case study <i>A. Walker</i>		case study <i>A. Walker</i>	Departure Gala Dinner: 19:00h	case study <i>A. Walker</i>	Coherent X-rays and applications <i>M. Fajardo</i>	
20:00h	Dinner	Welcome Drink										
		Dinner	Dinner	Dinner	Dinner	Dinner	Dinner	Dinner	Gala Dinner	Dinner	Dinner	

Fig.1 Time table of the school on high gradient wake acceleration

3. Student grants and sponsors

A considerable number of student grants was available for those participants who needed financial support to attend the school.

Several sponsors contributed to this item and provided support for all in all 14 student grants that were used to cover the students' fees for the school.

The list of sponsors includes:

IST (Instituto Superior Technico, that acted as well as local organiser)

ARIES and EuroNNac

DESY, Hamburg

CERN, Geneva

Ecole Polytechnique, Paris

Imperial College, London

Beyond that, the school got the official endorsement of the ICFA Committee (International Committee for Future Accelerators).

4. Audience and Lecturers

The school was planned from the beginning as a truly European and even international event. The school welcomed 70 students from 25 different nationalities, among them, beyond Europe, China, United States and Japan. The detailed distribution of students' nationalities is presented in the table below:

Nationality	Swiss	Armenian	Austrian	Brazilian	Chinese	Danish	French	German	Georgian	Indian	Iranian	Italian	Israeli	Japanese	South Korean	Malasian	Norwegian	Portuguese	Romanian	Russian	Spanish	Thai	Tunisian	British	American
	1	2	1	1	3	1	1	12	1	2	2	6	3	1	2	1	1	5	1	3	2	1	1	10	6

26 lecturers from 11 countries were giving courses, seminar talks or acting as tutors for the more practical work, the so-called case studies, where the students are asked to apply what they had learned and thus to do actual design work under the leadership of experienced colleagues.

Fig. 2 Students and lecturers during the excursion day in Lisbon.

5. Social Events and Networking

Several social events were included as integral part of the event to foster the communication and networking aspect of the school:

A free afternoon, where students could get together to get to know each other, exchange experience, join for homework and case studies – or – as well accepted just to relax.

A full day at the end of the first week was dedicated to an excursion to Lisbon with visits to places of cultural and historical interest.

Finally, a gala dinner in the mid of the second week established the frame for a relaxing and entertaining atmosphere and at the same time gave the chance to get into contact with other students and – equally important – to the teachers.

6. Future plans and conclusion

The series of lectures on high gradient wake acceleration presented an impressive spectrum of topics that are being studied at the moment in this new field of research. Key players from many institutes came together to present – in a highly didactic manner – their field of research to the students and to train the younger members of the community.

The present deliverable D5.1 is closely related to the ARIES work package 2, “Training, Communication and Outreach for Accelerator Science (TCO)” and covers a sub-topic of it.

It represents a valuable contribution to the teaching activities within ARIES and beyond, and fills a gap in training in oral and written form in this fast-developing field of novel acceleration techniques.

As part of the training aspect and integral part of the school it is planned to present the topics in written form, as “CERN yellow report”. It will be an up-date and follow up of the proceedings of a previous CAS on Plasma wake acceleration, that are available in printed and electronic form under the reference [CERN-2016-001](#).

While access to the slides of the present lectures is already available via the web page of the school, it is planned to have the new proceedings in printed form available for spring 2020.